

An Analytical Study of Stress and Personality among the College Students of Different Stream in Agra Division

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Abstract

Introduction: The objective of this study was to investigate the stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division. Another purpose of the study was to find out the stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division.

Methods: The subjects was selected through simple random sampling in which total 400 male students were taken as sample and 200 students were selected in Agra Division. Further 200 students sub-divided in to four streams equally i.e Physical Education, Arts & Humanities, Science and Commerce (50 each). The age of the subject was range from 18 to 24 years. All subjects were the resident of India. A stand and progressive matrices organizational selected stress among college students of different stream in Agra Division, **Academic Stress Questionnaire** by Mohd. Akram, Mohd. Ilyas Khan & Sabiha Baby and personality among college students of different stream, Dimensional Personality Inventory by Dr. Mahesh Bhargava was used. To find out significant different of stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division, the one-way analysis of variance was used. The level of significance was set at .05 levels.

Results and Discussion: The result reveals the one-way analysis of variance that there was significant ($p > .05$) for stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division.

Stress, Personality, Stream, Students.

Keywords

Introduction

"Education is the creation of sound mind in a sound body It develops man's faculty, especially his mind, so that he may be able to enjoy the contemplation of supreme truth, goodness and beauty in which perfect happiness essentially consists."

Education is the reconstruction of events that compose the lives of the individuals so that new happenings and new events become more purposeful and meaningful. (Bucher & Charles A., 1997)

Psychology is the study of human behavior. It is the study of man-man as a living human being, acting in an ever-changing world, responding to things, events and other people. Psychology deals with the behavior of man as it appears in his responses and with consciousness as he finds it in his immediate experience.

Sports psychology is the branch of science which deals with the mental health of the sportsmen. It is a sub-category of psychology which aims at improving sports performance, mainly based on the scientific study of physical and mental behavior of people towards sports. It tries to understand the 'how and why' behind it and concerns with the activity of mental processes in connection to the performance.

Stress is a non-specific response of the body to any demand made upon it or to external stimuli. A more practical definition is "When the problems presents by everyday life exceed our resources for coping with them, one feels stressed." Moreover, stress can also be generated from within by hopes, fears, expectations and beliefs.

Stress involves integrated activities of: Cortex, Hypothalamus, (automated nervous system) Neuromuscular and Hormonal system. Imbalances in brain chemistry particularly in neurotransmitter level have a large range of effects on:

1. Emotions
2. Behavior
3. Brain & body coordination.

Stress causes a reaction within the nervous system, stress hormone 'Cortical' is over-produced which leads to weakening and decreasing in the production of the calming hormones 'melatonin' and 'serotonin' occurs. With subsequent production of free radicals stress hormones may actually damage the brain when stress is sustained. Toxins and free radicals kill cells in every organ of the body. Organs that suffer the most cell damage at initial stage are the brain, liver, pancreas, adrenals, stomach and GI tract, which ultimately lead to weakening of whole nervous system and body immunology.

Even though it has been known for a long time that psychology influences athletic performance, an increasing number of psychologists and sports specialists are focusing on various study fields. They aim to investigate the underlying causes of athletic success and failure from a more holistic and in-depth perspective. In addition, one of their goals is to address the psychological disparities that exist among athletes competing in various sports in order to be in a position to provide timely assistance.

Objective of study

The objective of this study was to investigate the stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division. Another purpose of the study was to find out the stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division.

Review of Literature

Characteristics of the individual are well-suited to the particulars of the sporting domain being trained in, as well as the objectives and difficulties of that domain. Athletes tend to have personalities that are low in neuroticism, high in extraversion and diligence, and average in openness to experience and diligence. Despite these similarities, athletes do not have identical personality profiles simultaneously. Since the athletic training discipline had such a significant influence on it, as well as the fact that the personality determinants of the athletes are dependent on it, it is not easy to differentiate and define the personality type that is most advantageous among athletes. It has also been shown that there is a connection between certain personality qualities and the amount of time spent participating in sports; specifically, the longer and more intensely someone participates in sports, the more apparent their "sporting" personality becomes. As a result, the assumption may be made that athletes' (players') personalities are molded by their participation in sports, which is distinctive to individual sports. **(Singh R. & Patel S. K., 2023)**

Methodology

The subjects was selected through simple random sampling in which total 400 male students were taken as sample and 200 students were selected in Agra Division. Further 200 students sub-divided in to four streams equally i.e Physical Education, Arts & Humanities, Science and Commerce (50 each).The age of the subject was range from 18 to 24 years. All subjects were the resident of India. A stand and progressive matrices organizational selected stress among college students of different stream in Agra Division, **Academic Stress Questionnaire** by **Mohd. Akram, Mohd. Ilyas Khan & Sabiha Baby** and personality among college students of different stream, Dimensional Personality Inventory by Dr. Mahesh Bhargava was used. To find out significant different of stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division, the one-way analysis of variance was used. The level of significance was set at .05 levels.

Analysis

Stress:

To find out stress among different stream college students in Agra Division, analysis of variance was used and presented in table no.-1.

Table No.-1

Analysis of variance of stress among different stream college students in Agra Division.

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-ratio
Between Group	3	16859.86	5619.95	121.611*
Within Group	196	9057.64	46.212	

Significant at .05 level

F-Value required to be significant (3, 196) = 2.65

The values shown in table no. 1 clearly show that the calculated F-value of stress is much higher than the value required for significance. Therefore, post hoc test has been used to find out the difference in stress among different stream college students in Agra Division. The calculation of which is presented in table no.2 and shown by figure no.1.

Physical Education	Arts & Humanities	Science	Commerce	M.D	C.D
42.40	50			-7.6	2.66*
42.40		67.46		-25.06	
42.40			56.34	-13.94	
	50	67.46		-17.46	
	50		56.34	-6.34	
		67.46	56.34	11.12	

The post hoc test is to compare the stress among different stream college students in Agra Division. It has clearly revealed the significant difference between the students of Physical Education and Art & Humanities where the calculated mean difference found (-7.6), Physical Education and Science where the calculated mean difference found (-25.06), Physical Education and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-13.94), Art & Humanities and Science where the calculated mean difference found (-17.46), Art & Humanities, Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-6.34), Science and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (11.12) was higher than the required critical difference value 2.66 at .05 level of significant.

The scores are also illustrated in the figure no.-1

Personality:

To find out personality among different stream college students in Agra Division, analysis of variance was used and presented in table no.-3.

Table No.-3

Analysis of variance of personality among different stream college students in Agra Division.

Source of Variance	df	SS	MSS	F-ratio
Between Group	3	6326.62	2108.873	51.892*
Within Group	196	7965.36	40.640	

Significant at .05 level

F-Value required to be significant (3, 196) = 2.65

The values shown in table no. 3 clearly show that the calculated F-value of personality is much higher than the value required for significance. Therefore, post hoc test has been used to find out the difference in personality among different stream college students in Agra Division. The calculation of which is presented in table no. 4 and shown by figure no. 2.

Physical Education	Arts & Humanities	Science	Commerce	M.D	C.D
93.18	82.42			10.76	2.499*
93.18		77.66		15.52	
93.18			84.78	8.4	
	82.42	77.66		4.76	
	82.42		84.78	-2.36	
		77.66	84.78	-7.12	

The post hoc test is to compare the personality among different stream college students in Agra Division. It has clearly revealed the significant difference between the students of Physical Education and Art & Humanities where the calculated mean difference found (10.76), Physical Education and Science where the calculated mean difference found (15.52), Physical Education and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (8.4), Art & Humanities and Science where the calculated mean difference found (4.76) and Science and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-7.12) was higher than the required critical difference value 2.499 at .05 level of significant. But insignificant difference between the students of Art & Humanities and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-2.36) was lower than the required critical difference value 2.499 at .05 level of significant.

The scores are also illustrated in the figure no.-2

Result and Discussion

The present investigation was designed to know the stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division. The purpose of this study was revealed some specific differences for stress and personality among the college students of different stream in Agra Division. The research scholars did not intend to explore personal life of students. Various tools have been used to find out the important differences in aspects of stress and personality of students to achieve the purpose of this research.

The result of the study revealed significant difference among the mean scores of different stream college students in Agra Division in relation to stress and personality. This fact can be attributed to the different academic streams of the students, as all the students live in Agra Division and study in different streams (physical education, arts and humanities, science and commerce), due to which differences have been found in the speed and agility of all these students. The result of present study is also on the line of the studies conducted by Dr. Kumar Basant & Dr. Hada Sangeeta Singh (2023), conduct a study on topic “A Comparative Study of Personality Traits of Senior Secondary School Students of Government and Private Schools” and Sutradhar Aniket, Dr. Sen Subir, Adhikari Anasuya & et al (2023), conduct a study on topic “Self-Efficacy, Depression, Anxiety and Stress of University Students: A Study by Mahalanobis Distance”.

Conclusion

1. F-value of stress is much higher than the value required for significance. Therefore, post hoc test has been used to find out the difference in stress among different stream college students in Agra Division.
2. The post hoc test is to compare the stress among different stream college students in Agra Division. It has clearly revealed the significant difference between the students of Physical Education and Art & Humanities where the calculated mean difference found (-7.6), Physical Education and Science where the calculated mean difference found (-25.06), Physical Education and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-13.94), Art &

Humanities and Science where the calculated mean difference found (-17.46), Art & Humanities, Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-6.34), Science and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (11.12) was higher than the required critical difference value 2.66 at .05 level of significant.

3. F-value of personality is much higher than the value required for significance. Therefore, post hoc test has been used to find out the difference in personality among different stream college students in Agra Division.
4. The post hoc test is to compare the personality among different stream college students in Agra Division. It has clearly revealed the significant difference between the students of Physical Education and Art & Humanities where the calculated mean difference found (10.76), Physical Education and Science where the calculated mean difference found (15.52), Physical Education and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (8.4), Art & Humanities and Science where the calculated mean difference found (4.76) and Science and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-7.12) was higher than the required critical difference value 2.499 at .05 level of significant. But insignificant difference between the students of Art & Humanities and Commerce where the calculated mean difference found (-2.36) was lower than the required critical difference value 2.499 at .05 level of significant.

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